

The CAM Model: An *in vivo* Testbed for Molecular Communication Systems

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Abstract—Molecular communication (MC) research is increasingly focused on applications within the human body, such as health monitoring and drug delivery, which require testing in realistic and living environments. Thus, elevating experimental MC research to the next level requires developing realistic *in vivo* experimental testbeds. In this paper, we introduce the chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) model as the first versatile 3D *in vivo* MC testbed. The CAM itself is a highly vascularized membrane formed in fertilized chicken eggs and the CAM model has gained significance in various research fields, including bioengineering, cancer research, and drug development. Its versatility, reproducibility, and realistic biological properties make it perfectly suited for next-generation MC testbeds, facilitating the transition from proof-of-concept systems to practical applications. In this paper, we provide a comprehensive introduction to the CAM model, its properties, and its applications in experimental research. Additionally, we present a characterization of the CAM model as an MC system. As an experimental study, we investigate the distribution of fluorescent molecules in the closed-loop vascular system of the CAM model. We derive an analytical model based on the wrapped normal distribution to describe the propagation of particles in dispersive closed-loop systems, where the propagation of particles is mainly influenced by diffusion and flow. Based on this analytical model, we propose parametric models to approximate the particle propagation dynamics inside the CAM model. The model parameters are estimated via curve fitting to experimental results using a nonlinear least squares method. We provide a dataset containing experimental results for 69 regions in 25 eggs, on which we evaluate the proposed parametric models. Moreover, we discuss the estimated parameters, their relationships, and plausibility. Furthermore, we investigate and develop a parametric model for the long-term behavior of particles in the CAM model and their accumulation in the chick embryo's liver.

Index Terms—Chorioallantoic Membrane, Molecular Communication, Wrapped Normal Distribution, Diffusion, Indocyanine Green, ICG Accumulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic molecular communications (MC) is an emerging interdisciplinary research field at the intersection of life sciences and engineering [2]. MC naturally occurs in biological systems and is envisioned to enable communication between synthetic nanomachines and biological entities. In recent years, numerous potential applications of MC have been identified

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Fig. 1: Schematic illustration of the CAM model consisting of the chicken embryo, the yolk bag, and the CAM. Furthermore, a tumor is engrafted on the CAM (Created with BioRender.com).

across various sectors, including industry, environmental monitoring, and medicine [3], [4]. Despite the recent increase of experimental work, most MC research remains theoretical. Bridging the gap between theoretical concepts and their practical applications is a significant challenge [5]. In the medical sector, MC often focuses on in-body applications, necessitating the validation of concepts and technologies in realistic *in vivo* environments. However, many promising MC technologies are highly invasive and disruptive, making animal or human testing very difficult and currently almost impossible.

Experimental work on in-body MC is often focused on concepts for exchanging information between in-body devices, such as mobile nanosensors patrolling the cardiovascular system, and devices for the controlled delivery of drug molecules, and their experimental validation. Hereby, most testbeds established so far employ a tube-like channel (e.g., pipes or microfluidic chips) as a rough approximation of the cardiovascular system, where the signaling molecules are injected via a syringe or a valve [6]–[14]. In [7], a tube-based MC testbed employing biocompatible magnetic nanoparticles was developed. This system featured an electronic pump acting as the transmitter (TX), alongside a second pump to ensure a consistent background flow for signal propagation. On the receiver (RX) side, a susceptometer was installed to generate electrical signals as the magnetic particles traversed through it. In [8], a prototype platform for molecule shift keying was proposed. The system comprised an infusion pump and valves as TX, a tube-based microfluidic channel, and a compact charge-coupled device (CCD) as RX. The RX detected fluorescence signals emitted by graphene quantum dots (GQDs), which served as signaling particles. In [9],

a nanomaterial-based MC testbed was proposed to mimic the cardiovascular system. Color pigments were employed as signaling molecules, which were detected by a color sensor as RX. In [10], a fluid-based testbed was reported employing a channel consisting of a network of tubes, two peristaltic pumps as TXs, and an electrical conductivity sensor as RX. A similar testbed was recently proposed in [11], where the information was encoded into the pH level of the fluid. The authors in [14], [15] proposed a closed-loop fluid-based testbed employing the green fluorescent protein dreiklang (GFPD) as a reversibly switchable biocompatible signal molecule. In [12], the authors recently introduced a fluid-based testbed using animal blood as propagation medium and flesh to replicate the damping effects of skin and tissue on signal detection. As signaling molecule, biocompatible indocyanine green (ICG) was employed and the concentration at the RX was measured by an optical intensity sensor. The animal flesh was placed between the propagation channel and the sensor to mimic properties of human skin. Furthermore, in [16], the authors proposed an MC system based on the sciatic nerve of a bullfrog, which was extracted from the animal and isolated in a controlled environment. Electrical signals stimulated one end of the nerve and were recorded at the other end to evaluate the channel impulse response and the stimulation threshold of the nerve trunk. In [17], the authors performed experiments on different plants to measure the amplitude and duration of voltage changes associated with multiple action potentials and multiple mechanosensitive activation signals. For a more comprehensive overview on experimental MC research, we refer to [5], [18]. All testbeds reported in [6]–[12], [14]–[17] try to mimic realistic signal propagation environments or application scenarios. For example, studying blood [12], plants [17], or nerves extracted from a bullfrog [16] as propagation environment, biocompatible signaling particles such as ICG [12], GQDs [8], magnetic nanoparticles [7] or GFPD [14], and closed-loop systems [15] is important for gaining insight into the operation of MC systems under real-world conditions. Although these testbeds can successfully model some properties of real-world environments, provide a controllable setup, and allow the evaluation of the relevance of some parameters for MC system design, they are still far away from realistic application environments such as the cardiovascular system. In fact, despite the significant progresses in experimental MC research in the last few years, the influence of realistic and living - *in vivo* - environments on MC system design has not been comprehensively investigated, yet. In order to enable the practical deployment of synthetic MC systems in the future, it is indispensable to elevate experimental MC research to the next level by developing *in vivo* testbeds. With this in mind, in this paper, we propose a 3D *in vivo* MC testbed based on the chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) model, which provides an accessible model of a cardiovascular system including blood circulation and organs, see Fig. 1.

The CAM itself is a highly vascularized membrane which is found in the eggs of certain amniotes like birds and reptiles [19] and functions as a respiratory organ during embryo development [20], [21]. Moreover, human cells or tissues can be grafted onto the CAM, e.g., to study the effect

of therapeutics. Over the years, the CAM model has been established in different research fields and was originally used for angiogenic¹ and anti-angiogenic therapeutic approaches. In recent years, however, it has gained importance in many different fields, such as bioengineering, transplant biology, cancer research, patient derived xenograft (PDX) research, and drug development [23]–[25]. As the CAM model represents a simple and accessible *in vivo* model, it is perfectly suited as next-generation MC testbed. Therefore, in this paper, we propose the CAM model as a versatile and realistic model of an *in vivo* system for the validation and optimization of MC technologies, to enable the transition from simple proof-of-concept MC systems towards practical applications [1], [26]. As a first step, to characterize the CAM model as an MC system, we investigate the particle distribution and accumulation inside the CAM model's vascular system. To this end, we developed an experimental setup where we inject the fluorescent molecule ICG into the CAM's vascular system and measure the ICG intensity with a fluorescence camera. From the measurements it can be observed that injected particles distribute very fast inside the vascular system and after a steady state phase characterized by a uniform particle distribution, particles start to accumulate in the yolk bag and organs of the CAM model. Based on this observation, we show that the particle distribution in the CAM model can be divided into three phases, i.e., a *transient*, a *steady state*, and an *accumulation phase*. To characterize the different distribution phases, we develop parametric models based on the wrapped normal distribution, capable of describing the particle distribution in highly-vascularized closed-loop systems. The parametric models are fitted to experimental measurement data by a nonlinear least squares method to demonstrate their validity and to show their capability of providing valuable insights regarding characteristic effects occurring in living environments. Moreover, the accuracy of the proposed parametric models is evaluated by the root mean square error (RMSE). The main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- For the first time, we propose the CAM model as a versatile and accessible *in vivo* MC testbed, characterize its properties, and discuss its capabilities for the analysis and design of future MC systems.
- We experimentally investigate the distribution of the fluorescent molecule ICG inside the CAM model. Our experiments show that particles quickly distribute uniformly in the CAM model, before they accumulate in organs. We characterize the ICG distribution in the CAM model into three distinct phases, i.e., the *transient phase*, representing the fast distribution in the vascular system, the *steady state phase*, when particles are uniformly distributed inside the vascular system, and the *accumulation phase*, when particles start to accumulate in the organs of the embryo.
- We derive an analytical model based on a wrapped normal distribution, capable of describing the particle distribution in dispersive closed-loop systems. We validate the model by a comparison with results from particles-based

¹Angiogenesis is the formation of new blood vessels [22].

simulations (PBS). Inspired by the analytical model, we propose a basic parametric model and show that it is capable of approximating the transient and steady state particle distribution behavior in the CAM model by fitting the model parameters to experimental measurement data.

- We extend the basic parametric model to account for additional topological properties of vascularized networks, such as branching and the possible existence of multiple loops. We show that the extended model is in very good agreement with the experimental data for the transient and steady state distributions of particles inside the CAM model. Moreover, we show that the physical model parameters obtained for the proposed model via fitting to experimental measurements are consistent and plausible.
- We present an initial experimental study on the accumulation of particles in the liver of the embryo, which is a natural clearance mechanism of the CAM model. Moreover, we propose a first simple model to approximate the accumulation of particles in the liver and validate it by a comparison with experimental results.
- We created an experimental dataset containing 69 measurements in 25 eggs on different days of embryonic development (DED). The dataset contains measurements of the ICG distribution inside the CAM model and all parameter estimation results obtained for the developed parametric models. The dataset is shared with the community and will be continuously extended [27].

Compared to the conference version [1] of this paper, we model the distribution of ICG inside the CAM model more carefully and divide it into three phases, i.e., the *transient phase*, *steady state phase*, and *accumulation phase*. We extend the parametric model proposed for the molecule distribution in [1] to a mixture of wrapped normal distributions to capture the dynamics of the particle distribution in dispersive closed-loop systems. We demonstrate that the extended parametric model is capable of approximating the particle distribution in the CAM model more accurately compared to the model proposed in [1]. Moreover, we analyze the accuracy of the proposed parametric models based on the RMSE between the results obtained for the proposed models and experimental measurements. Furthermore, we investigate the ICG accumulation in the embryo's liver and present a corresponding simple parametric model. Moreover, we created a dataset containing experimental measurement data of the transient and steady state distribution of ICG inside the CAM model [27].

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section II, we introduce the CAM model, its advantages and disadvantages, topology, and applications. In Section III, we characterize the CAM model from an MC point of view and propose an analytical model for the distribution of molecules in dispersive closed-loop systems. In Section IV, we introduce the proposed parametric models to capture the dynamics of the ICG injection, distribution in the CAM vascular system, and accumulation in the embryo's liver. Section V is divided into two parts. First, the proposed parametric models are employed to approximate the distribution of molecules inside the CAM vascular system during the *transient* and *steady state phases*

by fitting their parameters to experimental measurement data. Moreover, a comprehensive discussion of the estimated model parameters is provided, and the dataset is described in detail. Second, the accumulation of ICG molecules in the embryo's liver during the *accumulation phase* is studied and the proposed parametric model is used to approximate the dynamics of particle accumulation. In Section VI, we discuss the results obtained in this paper and propose several directions for future research. Our conclusions are presented in Section VII, and the methodology for conducting the experiments is detailed in Appendix A.

II. THE CHORIOALLANTOIC MEMBRANE MODEL

In this section, we provide a comprehensive overview on the CAM model. We first provide a short introduction to the CAM model, and discuss its advantages and limitations for experimental research. Then, we outline the main research directions within the CAM literature. Since the CAM model has not been considered before in the MC community, we provide an overview of its components, describe the main physical parameters of the developing vascular system, and explain the growing importance of the CAM model in fields relevant for the MC community such as tumor and drug distribution research. After introducing the CAM model in this section, we will show that it can be interpreted as an MC system in Section III.

A. Introduction to the CAM Model

The CAM is formed in fertilized chicken² eggs as a highly vascularized extraembryonic membrane that functions as a respiratory organ during the embryo's development [21]. For over a century, scientists have utilized the CAM model in medical research, as it can serve as a realistic model for *in vivo* systems, bridging the gap between preclinical research and clinical trials [20]. As early as 1911, Rous and Murphy grafted chicken sarcoma cells onto the CAM model and observed tumor growth [28]. A year later, Murphy published the successful heterologous transplantation of tumors to the CAM model [29]. In the 1930s, the CAM was exploited for the first time for the cultivation of viruses and bacteria [30], [31]. Later, the CAM model was also used for vascular studies, such as blood vessel development and testing of pro-angiogenic and anti-angiogenic properties of substances [32]–[36]. The CAM model also has been extensively employed for *in vivo* experiments to investigate angiogenesis [37], [38], and human tumor growth and therapy [39], [40]. Human cells, PDX, and tissue can be engrafted onto the CAM, e.g., to study the effect of potential therapeutics, or to investigate angiogenic and anti-angiogenic processes involving tissue and cells. As a result, numerous substances have been reported to either promote or inhibit angiogenesis in the CAM model, including growth factors, anti-cancer agents, pro-angiogenic molecules,

²Although the CAM is present in many amniotes, including birds and reptiles, it is most commonly studied in fertilized chicken eggs. Due to their widespread availability and the extensive related literature, the term 'CAM' is conventionally used to refer to the vascularized extraembryonic membrane in fertilized chicken eggs.

natural and synthetic compounds, antibodies, organometallic compounds, and antibiotics [41].

B. Benefits and Limitations

In general, the CAM model is considered to be a flexible pharmaceutical testing platform with several advantageous and disadvantageous features [42], [43]. The CAM model provides the following benefits. First, the chick embryo grows into a fully developed organism, with vital organs such as heart and liver. The CAM model provides nutrients and has impressive capabilities for angiogenesis, making it an ideal tool for modeling more complex biological systems. During early development, chick embryos lack a fully developed immune system, which not only reduces costs compared to using immune-compromised animals but also opens up new avenues for experimentation. Furthermore, CAM experiments facilitate high-throughput screening [44], [45], allowing researchers to visualize results in real time. In addition, each egg can be used for multiple tests, and the highly vascularized nature of the CAM creates a perfect backdrop for studying tumor growth. Moreover, CAM research is cost-effective, as the eggs are small (6 cm length and 4 cm diameter), and easy to replace. Finally and maybe most importantly, the CAM model fulfills the 3R principles for the reduction, refinement, and replacement of animal models for research purposes [46].

Despite these advantages of the CAM model, there are also some drawbacks, of course. One significant challenge is the rapid growth of the embryo, which necessitates continuous monitoring to capture developmental changes. However, continuous monitoring is challenging, as the chick embryo cannot be kept outside the incubator for more than a few hours. Additionally, distinguishing between the established vascular network and newly formed capillaries can be challenging. Moreover, the CAM is quite sensitive to its surroundings; even slight changes in pH, temperature, or oxygen levels can impact experimental results. A further drawback can occur during drug studies in the CAM model, as the way drugs are metabolized in the CAM can differ from how they are processed by mammals [47].

C. Main Research Directions

In the CAM literature, two main research directions are widely recognized: (i) preclinical studies – with a particular emphasis on angiogenesis, cancer research, and drug screening – and (ii) the development of imaging and quantification techniques for vascular analysis and drug monitoring.

Due to its strong vascularization, the CAM model has become a valuable platform for drug screening [48], [49] and vascular-targeting therapies [50]. It enables rapid evaluation of compounds affecting angiogenesis and vascular integrity. Recent advances have established the CAM model as a robust system for PDX implantation, supporting the long-term observation of tumor vascularization. This application is particularly impactful in cancer research, providing insights into tumor biology and facilitating biomarker studies [25], [51].

The research on the CAM model has also driven the development of imaging methods for the analysis of vascular

growth and drug effects [52]. These advancements allow for the quantification of vessel density, structure, and blood flow, supporting angiogenesis studies and drug efficiency assessments [53]. While traditional destructive methods like histology and stereology remain common, non-destructive approaches – including X-ray, MRI, ultrasound, optical imaging, and AI-assisted analysis – offer detailed visualization of vascular networks [54], [55]. These tools enable both structural and functional assessments, such as measuring blood flow and oxygenation, especially in tumor-bearing CAM models for evaluating vascular-targeted therapies.

D. Topology

As shown in Fig. 1, the CAM model includes three main elements: the chick embryo, the yolk bag, and the CAM. As previously described, the CAM is an extraembryonic membrane that is formed by the mesodermal fusion of allantois and chorion within the third and tenth DED [47], [56]. The CAM is comprised of a vast array of blood vessels and a dense capillary network. The vascular structure developing in the CAM is completely connected to and supplied by the embryo's vascular system and – depending on the DED – also to the organs of the embryo. The yolk bag is needed to nourish the embryo and takes over the function of organs such as the liver, until these organs have fully developed in the embryo. Therefore, the CAM model represents a realistic *in vivo* model of a circulatory system providing a highly complex branched closed-loop vascular system as well as several natural environmental effects such as various clearance mechanisms caused by organs.

E. Particle Propagation

Characterizing the influence of diffusion, flow, and vascularization on the propagation of particles inside the CAM model is not straightforward. One of the biggest challenges is the fact that the CAM is a constantly developing system [57], [58]. Depending on the DED, the vascular system in the CAM and in the embryo is changing significantly and therefore, the blood volume, average volume flux, and also other parameters depend on the DED [59]. Also, the effective local blood flow velocity in the CAM model strongly depends on the DED and possibly exhibits a large variance among different eggs. In [60, page 40], it has been shown that the blood flow velocity varies with time along the vessel. In [61], it has been shown that the flow profile is laminar and measured time-averaged mean velocities range from $1 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ – 1mm s^{-1} for vessel diameters ranging from 25 – 500 μm . In [62], it has been additionally shown that the topology of the CAM can be divided into feeding arterioles and draining venules having larger diameters, and secondary arterioles and venules with normally distributed diameters having means of 46.3 μm and 49 μm , respectively. Moreover, the authors of [62] showed that the measured effective blood flow velocities increase linearly with the vessel diameter [62, Fig. 4]. The influence of diffusion inside the CAM model depends on the properties of the particles injected and the occurring chemical reactions, e.g., the affinity and binding of molecules to serum proteins such as albumin [63].

Fig. 2: Photos of the ICG fluorescence intensity distribution and accumulation in the CAM model over time for a long-term experiment.

Fig. 3: Snapshots of the distribution of fluorescent molecules in the vascular system of the CAM model directly after injection via a syringe (left) and after a few seconds fully distributed (right).

Fig. 4: CAM model for tumor and distribution studies. Left: ICG injection into CAM vessels at $t = 0$ min and distribution in the vascular system. Right: ICG is accumulated in tumor tissue after ~ 15 min [26].

Depending on the DED, the yolk bag and the organs of the chick embryo can have a strong influence on the propagation of particles in the CAM model, as they introduce additional clearance and accumulation effects. As in the first DEDs, the yolk bag takes over the functions of the liver to filter toxic particles, particles entering the yolk bag will accumulate with a certain probability. In later DEDs, organs in the embryo (e.g., brain and liver) start to develop and particles accumulate there, too [26], [64]. ICG molecules accumulate preferably in the liver of the embryo as hepatocytes actively take up the particles through specialized transport mechanisms, and they resist being broken down by the metabolic processes [65], [66]. Inside hepatocytes, ICG is quickly released into bile without being altered, and it does not return to the bloodstream or get recycled through the liver and intestines. Figure 2 shows the ICG fluorescence intensity at different time instances after particle injection to further illustrate the particle propagation and accumulation processes inside the CAM model. After injection, the particles quickly distribute inside the vascular system. Then, the fluorescence intensity starts to increase at the location of the embryo (right side of the egg) for $t > 5.5$ min. At the same time, the ICG fluorescence intensity in the vascular system decreases. In particular, the ICG particles gradually move from the vessels into the organs of the embryo where they accumulate, i.e., considering the age of the embryo shown in Fig. 2 (DED > 10), particles preferably accumulate in the liver of the embryo [64], [66].

The analysis and modeling of particle propagation in blood vessels and organs is a central focus of MC research and its prospective applications [67]. For these applications, the CAM model can serve as a valuable *in vivo* MC system, providing a powerful platform to explore the potential and feasibility of MC technologies.

F. Tumor and Distribution Studies

The CAM model has become increasingly important for tumor research over the few last years. As previously described, it is employed to gain more insights into tumor biology, metastasis, drug distribution, and molecular screening [21], [47], [68]. Besides for research on tumor growth and metastasis [69], the CAM model is also utilized for analyzing the distribution of specific molecules during the development and testing of targeted therapeutics [26], [48].

One key challenge is understanding how molecules distribute and accumulate, as well as visualizing tumors effectively. To tackle this, fluorescence imaging offers a solution. It relies on injecting fluorescent molecules into the CAM model [26], [70], [71]. A fluorescent molecule, commonly used in the CAM model, is the near-infrared fluorescent agent ICG, which is mainly used for cancer imaging and image-guided surgeries in clinical settings [63]. Stimulated with light in the near-infrared range (750 nm and 950 nm), ICG starts to fluoresce, allowing visualization of vascular and anatomical structures

Fig. 5: Interpretation of the CAM model as closed-loop MC system with TXs, e.g., a syringe or a tumor, several natural receivers (nRXs), e.g., yolk bag, organs, tumor tissue, and several synthetic receivers (sRXs) (Created with BioRender.com).

(see Fig. 3). Due to its chemical composition, ICG interacts with membrane and macro-molecular serum proteins, including albumin, which is commonly enriched in many cancers [26], [63]. Therefore, ICG is often used in clinical practice for the intraoperative visualization of tumors [72]. Moreover, as ICG preferably accumulates in tumor tissue and partly shows similar properties as drug molecules, it can be employed in the CAM model to characterize and optimize the accumulation of molecules in tumor tissue as a basis for the design and optimization of drug delivery systems [26], [63], [72]. Figure 4 shows an example of the ICG distribution in the vascular system of the CAM model and its accumulation in tumor tissue [26]. This accumulation is indicative of the tumor's enhanced vascular permeability, which is a characteristic feature of the growing tumor microenvironment. The ability to visualize ICG uptake in real time provides valuable insight into the tumor's vascular structure and can be useful for assessing therapeutic interventions targeting tumors.

Investigating tumor and drug distribution is a core topic of targeted drug delivery research, which is one of the key applications of MC [73]. In this context, the CAM model can serve as a valuable *in vivo* MC system, providing an effective platform to explore the capabilities and practical feasibility of MC technologies.

III. CHANNEL MODELING

In this section, we derive an MC channel model for the particle propagation in dispersive closed-loop systems which is subsequently used to approximate the particle distribution inside the CAM model. To this end, first, we provide an interpretation of the CAM model as a closed-loop MC system. Then, based on observations from experimental measurements of the distribution and accumulation of particles inside the CAM model, we present our modeling assumptions. These assumptions are used to derive an analytical model for the molecule distribution in closed-loop systems. Finally, we validate the analytical model by a comparison to results obtained by PBS.

Fig. 6: Application-dependent specializations of system in Fig. 5. (a): Study of molecule distribution and accumulation, yolk bag and organs are RXs. (b): Study of molecule accumulation in tumors, engrafted tumor tissue is the RX, and the yolk bag and organs are part of the channel. (c): Anomaly detection or monitoring tasks, engrafted tumor tissue is the TX (Created with BioRender.com).

A. CAM Model as an MC System

Figure 5 shows a representation of the CAM model from Fig. 1 rearranged as an MC system. The system consists of TXs, e.g., a syringe or a tumor, and possibly multiple RXs where we distinguish between natural receivers (nRXs), such as the yolk bag, organs, and tumor tissue, and synthetic receivers (sRXs) such as localized measurement units. Between the TXs and RXs, the closed-loop vascular system of the CAM represents the channel.

Depending on the targeted application, the topology in Fig. 5 can be specialized as it is shown for three specific cases in Fig. 6. Figure 6 (a) shows the MC system topology if the distribution and accumulation of molecules injected into the CAM model are studied. In this scenario, depending on the DED, the yolk bag and organs can be interpreted as multiple RXs, where molecules accumulate. The closed-loop vascular system is the channel, which can be described by a time-variant, possibly nonlinear function $\bar{h}_a(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}, t)$, depending on a three-dimensional space variable \mathbf{x} , a set of environmental parameters \mathbf{p} (e.g., diffusion coefficient, velocity, length of the vessel), and time t . Hereby, the time-variance of the channel mainly arises from random movements of the embryo, its growth, and the non-constant blood flow. Figures 6 (b) and (c) show “point-to-point” MC systems, where a TX releases signaling molecules for an nRX or sRX. Figure 6 (b) shows a drug delivery system as a particular application, i.e., the

TX injects drug molecules into the CAM model and the accumulation in the tumor tissue can be first characterized and later optimized [26]. In this scenario, the nRX is human tumor tissue engrafted onto the CAM, see Fig. 4, and the organs and yolk bag are part of the closed-loop channel $\bar{h}_b(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}, t)$ influencing the propagation of drug molecules by degradation effects. Figure 6 (c) shows a health monitoring application, where tumor tissue, modulated by the TX, releases specific biomarkers into the closed-loop channel $\bar{h}_c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}, t)$, which can be detected by an sRX.

B. Modeling Assumptions

The topology of the CAM model is highly complex due to its vascularization and closed-loop character, and it is constantly changing over time and partly unknown. Therefore, the development of an exact model for the propagation of molecules is infeasible. So far, only individual vessel trees of the CAM vascular system have been modeled explicitly and simulated numerically for hemodynamic studies [61], [62]. However, besides their high computational cost, such numerical models provide only limited insight into the overall dynamics and limited applicability for analytical characterization. Therefore, we focus on the development of insightful approximate models to characterize the molecule distribution inside the CAM model.

Figure 7 shows experimental results for the distribution of the fluorescent molecule ICG inside the CAM model at different time instances (top of Fig. 7) and the fluorescence measured over time in region of interest (ROI) \mathcal{R} centered at $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}} \in \mathcal{A}$, where \mathcal{A} is the opened egg area observed by an ICG fluorescence camera. The setup corresponds to an MC system where the tip of the syringe injecting the ICG is the TX located at $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{T}}$, and the observation of fluorescence intensity $I(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ in the ROI corresponds to a transparent sRX located at $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}$ (bottom of Fig. 7). Assuming that the intensity of the ICG fluorescence is proportional to the ICG molecule concentration [74], from the figure, we make two main observations:

- (i) From the bottom left plot in Fig. 7 we observe that, after the injection, the ICG molecule distribution reaches a steady state inside ROI \mathcal{R} very quickly (after approximately 25 s). This is due to the laminar flow, dispersion, and turbulences introduced by the high vascularization and the closed-loop character of the CAM's vascular system [61], [62].
- (ii) From the bottom middle plot in Fig. 7 we observe that, after the steady state has been reached, the ICG molecules are absorbed from the vascular system into the yolk bag and organs of the CAM model, leading to fewer molecules in the ROI \mathcal{R} . Compared to the initial molecule distribution process, this molecule absorption process is much slower and occurs on the order of minutes. The bottom right plot in Fig. 7 shows the accumulation of the ICG molecules in the embryo's organs. Concurrently, we can observe that the fluorescence intensity increases in the organ's region as it decreases in the vascular system. Based on observations (i) and (ii), we divide the temporal dynamics of the particle distribution in the CAM model into

three phases, i.e., the *transient phase*, *steady state phase*, and *accumulation phase*. The *transient phase* describes the fast initial spread of molecules inside the CAM model's vascular system. In practice, this phase is also affected by the dynamics of the particle injection mechanism. The *steady state phase* represents a temporary steady state, which occurs after the *transient phase* once the injected particles are almost equally distributed in the vascular system. Finally, the *accumulation phase* represents all accumulation phenomena of particles, e.g., in the yolk bag and organs, whose dynamics are much slower than the transient distribution process (see Fig. 7). Thus, we characterize the dynamics of the observed ICG intensity $I(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ at any point $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}} \in \mathcal{A}$ as follows

$$I(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t) = \begin{cases} I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t) & t \leq t_{\text{acc}} , \\ I_{\text{acc}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t) & t > t_{\text{acc}} , \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ represents the *transient* and *steady state phases*, $I_{\text{acc}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ represents the *accumulation phase*, and t_{acc} is the time where the *steady state phase* ends and the *accumulation phase* starts. Based on the division in (1), we develop separate parametric models for the *transient* and *steady state phases* on the one hand and for the *accumulation phase* on the other hand. In the following, we derive a physically motivated analytical model for the particle distribution in a closed-loop system, which will be used as part of the parametric model to approximate $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ in the *transient* and *steady state phases*. Since the model for the *accumulation phase* proposed in this paper is not “physically motivated”, and we assume it is independent from the *transient* and *steady state phases*, the parametric model for the approximation of $I_{\text{acc}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ during the *accumulation phase* is presented in Section IV.

C. Diffusion and Flow in Closed-loop Systems

In order to develop a model for the *transient* and *steady state phases*, we first propose an analytical model for the propagation of molecules in dispersive closed-loop systems, which we will use in Section V as a parametric model to approximate the propagation of molecules between a TX and an RX inside the CAM's vascular network. As previously described, the exact modeling of the topology of the CAM's vascular system is infeasible. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 8, we approximate the 3D closed-loop highly vascularized system by a 3D closed-loop pipe of length L_{eff} . In the closed-loop pipe, molecules are transported by diffusion and flow. Thus, due to the high vascularization, we expect that the molecule transport inside the CAM's vascular system is highly dispersive. Therefore, we assume that molecule propagation occurs in the dispersive regime [75], and model the 3D pipe on the right hand side of Fig. 8 by a 1D Aris-Taylor dispersion model. In this case, we can describe the concentration of molecules $p(x, t)$ in the closed-loop pipe system in Fig. 8 by a 1D diffusion advection process as follows [76]

$$\partial_t p(x, t) = D_{\text{eff}} \partial_{xx} p(x, t) - v_{\text{eff}} \partial_x p(x, t) , \quad (2)$$

where ∂_t and ∂_{xx} denote first order partial time- and second order space derivative, respectively, and the space coordinate $x \in [0, L_{\text{eff}}]$ is along the pipe (see Fig. 8). Parameters D_{eff}

Fig. 7: Top (from left to right): Injection and distribution of ICG molecules in the vascular system and accumulation in the yolk bag and organs. Bottom: Measured fluorescence intensity in different ROIs, such as vascular system and organs of the embryo (Created with BioRender.com).

Fig. 8: Proposed approximative model for the distribution of molecules in closed-loop systems. Left: Closed-loop CAM vascular system. Right: Approximation as a closed-loop pipe with effective diffusion coefficient D_{eff} and effective velocity v_{eff} (Created with BioRender.com).

in $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ and v_{eff} in m s^{-1} denote the effective diffusion coefficient and effective flow velocity, respectively.

Equation (2) can be solved straightforwardly if we assume $L_{\text{eff}} \rightarrow \infty$ and a uniform molecule release at $x = 0$ and $t = 0$, yielding a normal distribution in x [75]

$$p_n(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sigma(t)\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu(t))^2}{2\sigma^2(t)}\right), \quad (3)$$

which has variance $\sigma^2(t) = 2D_{\text{eff}}t$ and is shifted along the x -axis by its mean $\mu(t) = v_{\text{eff}}t$. Solution (3) is commonly applied for the modeling of dispersive MC systems in infinitely long tubes [75], [77]. However, (3) cannot be applied for closed-loop systems with finite L_{eff} , such as the CAM model and many other envisioned application environments of MC, e.g., the human circulatory system [15].

To extend (3) to a closed-loop system with finite L_{eff} (see right hand side of Fig. 8), (2) has to be restricted to the domain $[0, L_{\text{eff}}]$ with periodic boundary conditions, i.e., $p(0, t) = p(L_{\text{eff}}, t)$ and $\partial_x p(0, t) = \partial_x p(L_{\text{eff}}, t)$. Then, (2) characterizes the 1D dispersive propagation of molecules on a circle with circumference L_{eff} . A solution to (2) with periodic boundary conditions for a uniform release at $x = 0$ and $t = 0$

is the wrapped normal distribution, which can be obtained from wrapping (3) to a circular domain [78]

$$p_{\text{wn}}(x, t) = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{L_{\text{eff}}\bar{\sigma}(t)} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{(\bar{x} - \bar{\mu}(t) + 2\pi k)^2}{2\bar{\sigma}^2(t)}\right), \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}^2(t) = \lambda^2\sigma^2(t)$, $\bar{\mu}(t) = \lambda\mu(t)$, and $\bar{x} = \lambda x$ denote the variance, mean, and position mapped on a circle of circumference L_{eff} with scaling parameter $\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{L_{\text{eff}}}$. The general behavior of (4) is depicted in Fig. 8. At time $t = 0$, molecules are concentrated at $x = 0$ and start to propagate, mainly driven by flow v_{eff} . Due to diffusion, variance $\bar{\sigma}^2$ is increasing over time and molecules are getting more and more dispersed. For $t \rightarrow \infty$, variance $\bar{\sigma}^2(t) \rightarrow \infty$, and the molecules are uniformly distributed in the closed-loop system. In Section IV, we will use (4) as an approximation for characterizing the channel characteristics $\bar{h}(x, p, t)$ of the CAM vascular system, i.e., $\bar{h}(x, p, t) \approx p_{\text{wn}}(x, t)$.

Inspecting $p_{\text{wn}}(x, t)$ in (4) and $p_n(x, t)$ in (3), it becomes clear that (3) corresponds to the term $k = 0$ on the right hand side of (4) for $\lambda = 1$. The other terms with $k \neq 0$ in the sum in (4) represent the contributions from multiple cycles in the closed-loop. For the scenario considered in Fig. 8, the closed-loop also affects the received signal, as a single release may cause multiple peaks in the average number of molecules observed at the RX. All peak times $\{t_{\text{max}}(k, d_{\text{rx}}) | k \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ observed by an RX located at d_{rx} (see Fig. 8) due to the molecules circulating multiple times in the loop, can be obtained by modifying the peak time for an infinitely long tube [77] as follows

$$t_{\text{max}}(k, d_{\text{rx}}) = \frac{D_{\text{eff}}}{v_{\text{eff}}^2} \left(-1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{v_{\text{eff}}^2}{D_{\text{eff}}^2} (d_{\text{rx}} + k L_{\text{eff}})^2} \right). \quad (5)$$

D. Analysis and Validation

To analyze the behavior of (4), we exemplarily consider a micro-scale closed-loop pipe system with length $L_{\text{eff}} = 1$ mm,

Fig. 9: Comparison between p_n in (3) (for an infinite length pipe) and p_{wn} in (4) (for a closed-loop pipe) at two different RX locations x_1 (top) and x_2 (bottom) for different effective diffusion coefficients D_{eff} .

radius $r_0 = 100 \mu\text{m}$, effective flow velocity $v_{\text{eff}} = 50 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$, and two different diffusion coefficients $D = [1.25, 5] \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, yielding a system operating in the dispersive regime [79]. The effective diffusion coefficient D_{eff} can be calculated as $D_{\text{eff}} = D(1 + \frac{1}{48}(\frac{r_0 v_{\text{eff}}}{D})^2)$ [77, Eq. (12)]. Molecules are released instantaneously at time $t = 0$ and position $x = 0$. To validate (4) and the modeling of the 3D pipe on the right hand side of Fig. 8 by a 1D drift-diffusion process, we compare our derived solution for the diffusion advection equation with periodic boundary condition to results from PBS, shown as green circles in Fig. 9.

We implemented the PBS in a 3D straight cylinder with reflecting inner boundaries. The cylinder is elongated along the x axis of a Cartesian coordinate system from $x = 0$ to $x = L_{\text{eff}}$. We realize the closed-loop characteristic of the straight boundary by connecting the two circular bases of the straight cylinder, i.e., particles moving to $x > L_{\text{eff}}$ in a simulation step are moved to $x \bmod L_{\text{eff}}$. At time $t = 0$, 10^4 particles are uniformly distributed over a disc representing the boundary of the cylinder at $x = 0$, and start diffusing for $t > 0$. In addition, they are affected by the laminar flow in x direction. The laminar flow we consider is radially symmetric with a parabolic profile, i.e., $v_x = 2v_{\text{eff}}(1 - (r/r_0)^2)$, where v_x , r , and r_0 are the particle's velocity in x direction, the distance of the particle from the x axis, and the radius of the cylinder. The PBS results (green circles) shown in Fig. 9 were obtained by averaging over 20 PBS realizations and a time step of 10^{-4} s.

Figure 9 shows the normalized concentration obtained with (3) and (4) for two different RX positions $x_1 = 0.39 \text{ mm}$ and $x_2 = 0.84 \text{ mm}$ (see also Fig. 8). The approximate peak times according to (5) are indicated by blue dots. From Fig. 9, we observe that p_{wn} (black curves) successfully captures the effects introduced by a closed-loop system, such as the repeated observation of molecules by the RX and the non-zero steady state concentration. In comparison, p_n (gray curve with markers) only captures the dynamics of the first peak as expected. An interesting effect, occurring in closed-loop systems is shown in the bottom plot of Fig. 9 (highlighted

by the red ellipse). For an RX position closely behind the TX and strong diffusion, an upstream peak occurs before the actual peak arrives at $t = 15$ s. This peak originates from molecules diffusing against the direction of flow into the RX region. All results are in good agreement with the results from PBS, validating that (4) is a suitable model for the propagation of molecules in dispersive closed-loop systems.

IV. PARAMETRIC MODELS AND CURVE FITTING

In this section, we use the assumptions and the analytical model from the previous section as a foundation. We then develop parametric models for particle injection and distribution in the CAM model during the *transient*, *steady state*, and *accumulation* phases. Moreover, we describe the employed fitting and parameter estimation methods and metrics to evaluate the performance of the proposed parametric models. The proposed parametric models are fitted to experimental measurement data in Section V to show their capability to approximate the particle distribution in the CAM model.

A. Parametric Models

As previously mentioned, the *transient phase* is strongly influenced by the particle injection dynamics. Therefore, we first present a parametric model to approximate the actual injection dynamics $f_{\text{inj}}(t)$. Then, we propose two parametric models to approximate the particle concentration $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ during the *transient* and *steady state* phases, based on the analytical model developed in Section III-C. Finally, we propose a first simple model to approximate the particle accumulation $I_{\text{acc}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ in the organs of the embryo within the CAM model.

1) *Injection Dynamics*: To approximate the actual particle injection dynamics $f_{\text{inj}}(t)$, we use a raised cosine function to account for the smoothness of the injection process, i.e.,

$$f_{\text{inj}}(t) \approx \hat{f}_{\text{inj}}(\mathcal{B}, t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{t_w} (1 - \cos(\omega(t - t_0))) & t_0 < t < t_w + t_0 \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathcal{B} = \{t_w, t_0\}$ is the parameter set, with t_w representing the injection duration and defining the period of the cosine function as $\omega = 2\pi/t_w$, and t_0 denoting the injection start time.

2) *Transient and Steady State Phases*: We propose two parametric models to approximate the particle distribution $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ in ROI \mathcal{R} , centered at $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}} \in \mathcal{A}$, during the *transient* and *steady state* phases based on the analytical model in (4). To emphasize the dependence of $p_{wn}(x, t)$ in (4) on the effective diffusion coefficient D_{eff} , effective flow velocity v_{eff} , effective length L_{eff} , and also the distance d_{rx} from the injection site, we denote the distribution in (4) in the following by $p_{wn}(\mathcal{Q}, t)$, where \mathcal{Q} denotes the parameter set, i.e., $\mathcal{Q} = \{D_{\text{eff}}, v_{\text{eff}}, L_{\text{eff}}, d_{\text{rx}}\}$. We note that, in reality, the blood flow velocity varies over time [60], and the effective flow velocity v_{eff} represents the mean value of the actual time-variant velocity inside the vascular system of the CAM model.

a) *Single Wrapped Normal Distribution*: We first propose a basic parametric model assuming that the complete vascular system of the CAM model can be represented by a single loop as described in Section III and shown in Fig. 8. To obtain an approximation of $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$, we combine $\hat{f}_{\text{inj}}(\mathcal{B}, t)$ from (6) with the analytical channel model $p_{\text{wn}}(\mathcal{Q}, t)$ from (4), as follows

$$I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t) \approx \hat{I}_{\text{dist}}(\mathcal{Q}, t) = \hat{f}_{\text{inj}}(\mathcal{B}, t) * p_{\text{wn}}(\mathcal{Q}, t), \quad (7)$$

where $*$ denotes temporal convolution.

b) *Multiple Wrapped Normal Distributions*: As discussed in Section II, the CAM model is highly vascularized. Therefore, to account for this complex branched topology, we propose an extended parametric model allowing for multiple loops, which might occur in the CAM vascular network. Thus, we extend (7) to the superposition of multiple wrapped normal distributions (4) characterized by different sets of physical parameters as follows

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t) &\approx \hat{I}_{\text{dist},n}(\mathcal{P}^n, t) \\ &= \hat{f}_{\text{inj}}(\mathcal{B}, t) * \sum_{j=1}^n a^{n,j} p_{\text{wn}}(\mathcal{Q}^{n,j}, t), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $a^{n,j}$ is a weight parameter, i.e., $\sum_{j=1}^n a^{n,j} = 1$, and the superscript j indicates the different wrapped normal distributions. The complete set of model parameters is given by $\mathcal{P}^n = \{\mathcal{P}^{n,1}, \dots, \mathcal{P}^{n,n}\}$, where $\mathcal{P}^{n,j} = \{a^{n,j}, \mathcal{Q}^{n,j}\} = \{a^{n,j}, D_{\text{eff}}^{n,j}, v_{\text{eff}}^{n,j}, L_{\text{eff}}^{n,j}, d_{\text{rx}}^{n,j}\}$ denotes the parameters belonging to the j -th term of the summation in (8). The total number of parameters is $n \times |\mathcal{P}^{n,j}|$, where $|\cdot|$ is the size of a set. For $n = 1$, (8) is equivalent to (7). We note that in the rest of the paper (7) and (8) are referred as the basic and the extended parametric models, respectively.

3) *Accumulation Phase*: As previously described in Sections III-B and II-E, and shown in Fig. 2, particles are very quickly uniformly distributed in the vascular system of the CAM model and reach a steady state before the fluorescence intensity slowly decreases in the vascular system and increases in the organs of the embryo during the *accumulation phase*. The acquisition of reliable measurement data for the accumulation in the embryo's organs is very challenging, mainly due to the movement of the embryo and possible concealment of the organs by other parts of the CAM model. In order to provide a comprehensive description of the molecule distribution in the CAM model, we propose the following simple parametric model for the accumulation of molecules in the organs of the embryo during the *accumulation phase*

$$I_{\text{acc}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t) \approx \hat{I}_{\text{acc}}(\mathcal{C}, t) = 1 - a \exp(-bt), \quad (9)$$

with parameter set $\mathcal{C} = \{a, b\}$. We note that, as more measurement data for the *accumulation phase* become available, we will further extend (9) to a physically motivated model for particle accumulation in future work.

B. Curve Fitting

After developing the parametric models in Section IV-A, we fit them to measured data in order to determine the

parameters. For all curve fittings based on the parametric models (6), (7), (8), and (9), we use Matlab's curve fitting toolbox implementing a nonlinear least squares method. The curve fitting and parameter estimation is performed based on the fluorescence intensity $I(\mathbf{x}, t)$ measured over time with an ICG camera focusing on the opened egg area \mathcal{A} with area size A^3 . In particular, $I(\mathbf{x}, t)$ denotes the measured fluorescence intensity of a region centered at \mathbf{x} in the open egg area \mathcal{A} . As the absolute numerical values of the measured fluorescence intensity are not physically meaningful, all measured intensities are normalized to their steady state value to ensure comparability within individual measurements. We employ the RMSE as a metric to evaluate the performance of the parametric models approximating the ICG dynamic.

1) *Injection Dynamics*: For the injection dynamics, we first calculate the mean fluorescence intensity $\bar{I}(t)$ in the open egg area \mathcal{A} , i.e., $\bar{I}(t) = \frac{1}{A} \int_{\mathcal{A}} I(\mathbf{x}, t) d\mathbf{x}$. Then, the actual injection dynamics can be obtained from the derivative of the mean intensity $\bar{I}(t)$, i.e., $f_{\text{inj}}(t) = \frac{d}{dt} \bar{I}(t)$. The derivative of the mean intensity $\bar{I}(t)$ is computed numerically as measurements are available only at discrete times $i\Delta t$, i.e., $\bar{I}(i\Delta t)$, where Δt is the sampling interval, $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$, and $N + 1$ is the total number of discrete-time samples within the observation interval. The numerical derivative is defined as $\frac{\Delta \bar{I}(i\Delta t)}{\Delta t} = \frac{\bar{I}(i\Delta t) - \bar{I}((i-1)\Delta t)}{\Delta t}$, and $\bar{I}(-\Delta t) = 0$. Hence, by fitting the parametric model $\hat{f}_{\text{inj}}(\mathcal{B}, t)$ to the measured injection dynamics $f_{\text{inj}}(t)$, t_w and t_0 can be jointly estimated. The nonlinear least squares curve fitting method solves the following optimization problem

$$\mathcal{B} = \arg \min_{\tilde{\mathcal{B}} \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{B}}} \sum_{i=0}^N \left(f_{\text{inj}}(i\Delta t) - \hat{f}_{\text{inj}}(\tilde{\mathcal{B}}, i\Delta t) \right)^2, \quad (10)$$

where the parameter set $\mathcal{B} \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{B}}$ minimizes the objective function (10), and $\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{B}} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ is the parameter search space.

2) *Transient and Steady State Phases*: For the approximation of the particle dynamics during the *transient* and *steady state phases*, we extract the localized fluorescence intensity $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ in a specific ROI $\mathcal{R} \subset \mathcal{A}$, centered at $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}$. As all physical parameters of the CAM vascular system are unknown or only given very vaguely in the literature, the parameter sets \mathcal{Q} in (7) and \mathcal{P}^n in (8) are estimated during the fitting process. Moreover, as the measured $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ reaches steady state very quickly, the initial slope is the most important feature for the fitting process, the actual fitting of (7) and (8) is performed based on the derivatives of the measured fluorescence intensity, i.e., $\frac{d}{dt} \hat{I}_{\text{dist}}(\mathcal{P}^n, t) \approx \frac{d}{dt} I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$. Hence, the nonlinear least squares method to obtain parameter sets \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{P}^n solves the following optimization problems

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Q} = \arg \min_{\tilde{\mathcal{Q}} \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{Q}}} \sum_{i=0}^N \left(\frac{\Delta}{\Delta t} I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, i\Delta t) \right. \\ \left. - \frac{\Delta}{\Delta t} \hat{I}_{\text{dist}}(\tilde{\mathcal{Q}}, i\Delta t) \right)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

³We assume the measured ICG fluorescence intensity is proportional to the ICG concentration in $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}$ [74].

$$\mathcal{P}^n = \arg \min_{\tilde{\mathcal{P}}^n \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{P}^n}} \sum_{i=0}^N \left(\frac{\Delta}{\Delta t} I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, i\Delta t) - \frac{\Delta}{\Delta t} \hat{I}_{\text{dist},n}(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}^n, i\Delta t) \right)^2, \quad (12)$$

where the optimal parameter sets $\mathcal{Q} \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{Q}}$ and $\mathcal{P}^n \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{P}^n}$ minimize the objective functions in (11) and (12), respectively, and $\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{Q}} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^4$ and $\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{P}^n} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{5n}$ are the corresponding parameter search spaces.

3) *Accumulation Phase*: For the approximation of the particle dynamics during the *accumulation phase*, we measure the fluorescence intensity $I_{\text{acc}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$. Parameter set \mathcal{C} is estimated via curve fitting of $\hat{I}_{\text{acc}}(\mathcal{C}, t)$ in (9) to measured fluorescence intensity during the *accumulation phase*, $I_{\text{acc}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$. Numerically, the fitting process to obtain the parameter set \mathcal{C} can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{C} = \arg \min_{\tilde{\mathcal{C}} \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{C}}} \sum_{i=0}^N \left(I_{\text{acc}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, i\Delta t) - \hat{I}_{\text{acc}}(\tilde{\mathcal{C}}, i\Delta t) \right)^2, \quad (13)$$

where the parameter set $\mathcal{C} \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{C}}$ minimizes the objective function in (13), and $\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{C}} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ is the parameter search space.

4) *Fitting Performance*: To evaluate the accuracy of the developed parametric models, an appropriate performance metric is crucial. As the fitting of the parametric models is applied to the entire dataset containing measurements of the *transient* and *steady state phases*, the data might contain additional noise and potentially unknown influencing factors. Thus, we choose the RMSE as performance metric due to its robustness to noisy data. The RMSE between a measurement $I_X(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ and its approximation $\hat{I}_X(\mathcal{V}, t)$ is defined as follows

$$\text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_X) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N \left(I_X(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, i\Delta t) - \hat{I}_X(\mathcal{V}, i\Delta t) \right)^2}, \quad (14)$$

where $X = \{\text{dist}, \cdot, (\text{dist}, n), \text{acc}\}$ and $\mathcal{V} = \{\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{P}^n, \mathcal{C}\}$ are placeholders to distinguish between the parametric models in (7), (8), and (9), respectively. In the following section, we will use the RMSE in (14) to evaluate the accuracy of the parametric models for the *transient* and *steady state phases* in (7) and (8) and the *accumulation phase* in (9).

V. EXPERIMENTAL ICG DISTRIBUTION STUDY

In this section, we present experimental and analytical results for the distribution of ICG molecules in the CAM model. Similar to the previous sections, we discuss the *transient* and *steady state phases* and the *accumulation phase* separately. First, we consider the *transient* and *steady state phases*. We briefly describe the employed measurement methods, and the prepared dataset containing the measurement data, estimated parameters, and approximated ICG distribution [27]. Then, we evaluate the approximation of the ICG injection dynamics by (6) exemplarily for three measurements contained in the dataset. Subsequently, the approximation of the ICG distribution in the *transient* and *steady state phases* based

on (7) and (8) is evaluated. Furthermore, we present the estimated parameters obtained for both parametric models and discuss their plausibility and consistency. Second, we study the *accumulation phase*. We describe the corresponding measurement process and related challenges. Then, we provide first measurement results for two eggs and compare with the results obtained for the parametric model (9).

A. Transient and Steady State Phases

1) *Measurement Process and Dataset Description*: For all measurements, we injected the fluorescent molecule ICG into the CAM vascular system via a syringe and the fluorescence intensity $I(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ was tracked by an ICG camera focusing on the open egg area \mathcal{A} . From the recordings, the ICG intensities $I(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ in different ROIs centered at $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}} \in \mathcal{A}$ were extracted and post-processed. In the experiments, we aimed to maintain consistent experimental conditions. A detailed description of the experimental preparation of the eggs is provided in Appendix A.

For the generated dataset, we performed experiments on 35 different eggs at different DEDs, where the measurements of ten eggs had to be excluded. We measured 125 ROIs on the 25 remaining eggs and obtained 69 reliable measurements. The two main reasons that caused the loss of eggs were bleeding after the ICG injection and the embryo's movement interfering with the measurements. In particular, after the removal of the injection needle, blood can spread on the surface of the CAM and distort the measurements. The embryo's movement results in unpredictable changes in the position of the vessels that were marked as ROI, which made a reliable tracking of the ICG intensity impossible. Based on the data successfully collected from 25 eggs we created a dataset for the particle distribution in the CAM model during the *transient* and *steady state phases*, which can be downloaded from [27]. The dataset is a *.mat* file and named *CAM_Data.mat*. This file contains all the data in a single variable of *table* type named *MetaData*. The *MetaData* variable contains the egg numbers, ROI numbers, parameter sets \mathcal{P}^1 and \mathcal{P}^2 , DED, injection duration, $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$, time vector, approximate parametric models $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$, $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$, images of the CAM, $\text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1})$, $\text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2})$, and injection distance d_{inj} , which is the distance between the injection point and the ROI of interest (e.g., the white double arrow in the CAM model image of Egg 20 in Fig. 12).

2) *Molecule Injection Dynamics*: The curves with markers in Fig. 10 show the measured mean fluorescence intensity $\bar{I}(t) = \frac{1}{A} \int_{\mathcal{A}} I(\mathbf{x}, t) d\mathbf{x}$ (top plot) and the injection dynamics $f_{\text{inj}}(t) = \frac{d}{dt} \bar{I}(t)$ (bottom plot) for three different eggs from the dataset. The dashed curves in the bottom plot of Fig. 10 show the approximation $\hat{f}_{\text{inj}}(\mathcal{B}, t)$ of $f_{\text{inj}}(t)$ according to (6) obtained by curve fitting alongside the estimated injection time t_0 and duration t_w . The resulting approximated mean intensity $\bar{I}(\mathcal{B}, t) = \int_0^t \hat{f}_{\text{inj}}(\mathcal{B}, \tau) d\tau$ is shown by the dashed curves in the top plot of Fig. 10. From both plots, it can be observed that the approximation $\hat{f}_{\text{inj}}(\mathcal{B}, t)$ obtained with the simple model (6) is in good agreement with the measured injection dynamics $f_{\text{inj}}(t)$ for all considered eggs.

Fig. 10: Top: Measured $\bar{I}(t)$ and fitted $\hat{I}(t)$ mean fluorescence intensity for three eggs. Bottom: Measured and fitted injection dynamics $f_{inj}(t)$ and estimated injection delays and duration.

3) Molecule Distribution in Transient and Steady State Phases:

a) *Single Wrapped Normal Distribution*: In the following, we evaluate the capability of the basic parametric model (7) to approximate the *transient* and *steady state* phases of molecule distribution in the CAM model (see Fig. 8 and Section III). Figure 11 shows the measured fluorescence intensity $I_{dist}(x_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ at $x_{\mathcal{R}}$ over time, for three eggs from the dataset (curves with colored markers). The black curves in Fig. 11 show the approximated fluorescence intensity $\hat{I}_{dist}(Q, t)$ obtained by curve fitting of (7) and the estimated parameter values for each measurement. The photos on the right hand side of Fig. 11 show the actual injection locations and the locations of ROIs \mathcal{R}_5 , \mathcal{R}_1 , and \mathcal{R}_2 for Egg 4, Egg 5, and Egg 6, respectively, shortly after the injection started. In general, all measurements are in line with the assumption that the *steady state* phase inside the vascular system is reached very quickly (see Section III-B). We observe from Fig. 11 that the overall shape of the measured $I_{dist}(x_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ is well reproduced by the proposed parametric model $\hat{I}_{dist}(Q, t)$. For example, for Egg 4 (top plot) the characteristic increases in the slope around 5 s, for Egg 5 (center plot) the peak around 4 s, and for Egg 6 (bottom plot) the initial slope are reproduced very well by the proposed model. However, for all eggs considered in Fig. 11, the basic parametric model (7) fails to capture the intensity drop (around 10 s), most prominently for Egg 6 in the bottom plot. Instead, approximation $\hat{I}_{dist}(Q, t)$ stays at the steady state. Despite this mismatch, the proposed basic parametric model in (7) is capable of approximating the complex behavior of the CAMs vascular system for a fixed injection-measurement (TX-RX) arrangement.

Next, we discuss the estimates obtained for the parameters Q of the basic model, which are also given in Fig. 11 for each egg considered. First, we can observe that the estimated value of v_{eff} is similar for all three eggs, and is in the range of values known for the CAM model from the literature (see Section II-D). The estimated D_{eff} values are in the range of 10^{-8} – $10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which exceeds the typical range of molecule diffusion coefficients by several orders of magnitude. However,

Fig. 11: Left: Three chosen measurements of the ICG distribution $I_{dist}(x_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ from the dataset (curves with markers) and approximations $\hat{I}_{dist}(Q, t)$ (solid curves) obtained with the basic parametric model in (7). Right: Photo of the considered eggs shortly after the injection. The specific ROI positions, $x_{\mathcal{R}_5}$, $x_{\mathcal{R}_1}$, and $x_{\mathcal{R}_2}$, are highlighted by a circle and an arrow. The numbers indicate the number of the ROI in a specific egg, e.g., \mathcal{R}_5 in Egg 4 is the fifth considered ROI where measurement data were obtained.

as the CAM system is highly vascularized and contains several sources of turbulence (cf. Section II-D), these large values are reasonable and reflect the expected dispersion, which is captured by the effective diffusion coefficient D_{eff} . Although the estimates obtained for the parameters of $\hat{I}_{dist}(Q, t)$ are not estimates of actual physical parameters in the CAM model and parametric models, the relationships between them seem meaningful.

b) *Multiple Wrapped Normal Distributions*: Next, we investigate the extended parametric model (8) for $n = 2$ and compare it with the basic model in (7). Figure 12 shows the fluorescence intensity $I_{dist}(x_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ measured at $x_{\mathcal{R}}$ over time, for six different eggs from the dataset (curves with blue markers). The green and red curves in Fig. 12 show the approximations obtained by fitting the parametric models $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(P^1, t)$ and $\hat{I}_{dist,2}(P^2, t)$ according to (7) and (8), respectively.

The photos on the right hand side of each plot show the injection and considered ROI locations (shown as white circle highlighted with an arrow) \mathcal{R}_3 , \mathcal{R}_2 , \mathcal{R}_3 , \mathcal{R}_5 , \mathcal{R}_4 , and \mathcal{R}_1 for Egg 1, Egg 3, Egg 4, Egg 19, Egg 20, and Egg 24, respectively, shortly after the injection started. Similar to Fig. 11, all measurements shown in Fig. 12 are in line with the assumption that the *steady state* phase inside the vascular system is reached very quickly (see Section III-B). Comparing the approximations obtained by the parametric models, we can observe that the extended model $\hat{I}_{dist,2}(P^2, t)$ is in very good agreement with the measurements and provides a much higher accuracy compared to the basic model $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(P^1, t)$. For all

Fig. 12: Experimental and fitting results for parametric models $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ and $\hat{I}_{dist,2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ for approximating the propagation of ICG molecules in the CAM vascular system, measured in specific ROIs for six different eggs. An example of the injection distance, d_{inj} , which indicates the distance between the injection point and the desired ROI, is shown with a white dashed double arrow in the image of Egg 20.

TABLE I: Estimated parameters for Fig. 12.

	DED	n	D_{eff} [$m^2 s^{-1}$]	v_{eff} [$mm s^{-1}$]	L_{eff} [cm]	d_{rx} [cm]	a
Egg 1, x_{R3}	15	1	$13.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$	9.4	5.6	2.1	1
		2	$(7.6 \cdot 10^{-6}, 9.7 \cdot 10^{-7})$	(2.9, 0.4)	(2.6, 1.3)	(0.64, 1)	(0.88, 0.12)
Egg 3, x_{R2}	15	1	$12 \cdot 10^{-6}$	9.9	4.4	4.1	1
		2	$(5.2 \cdot 10^{-5}, 4.5 \cdot 10^{-8})$	(11, 0.2)	(5.8, 6.1)	(0.4, 0.2)	(0.98, 0.02)
Egg 4, x_{R3}	15	1	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-8}$	8.9	4.1	0.0006	1
		2	$(3.4 \cdot 10^{-8}, 3.1 \cdot 10^{-6})$	(10, 0.04)	(7, 5.2)	(0.001, 1.4)	(0.65, 0.35)
Egg 19, x_{R5}	9	1	$1 \cdot 10^{-11}$	4.3	2.8	1.5	1
		2	$(3.4 \cdot 10^{-6}, 2.2 \cdot 10^{-7})$	(2.2, 0.5)	(3.6, 0.8)	(0.8, 0.7)	(0.39, 0.61)
Egg 20, x_{R4}	9	1	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	6.7	2.5	0.8	1
		2	$(3.9 \cdot 10^{-6}, 7.3 \cdot 10^{-6})$	(5.5, 5.3)	(2, 4.6)	(0.6, 0.5)	(0.83, 0.17)
Egg 24, x_{R1}	11	1	$6.8 \cdot 10^{-10}$	9.6	0.4	0.0007	1
		2	$(1.3 \cdot 10^{-5}, 2.4 \cdot 10^{-7})$	(10, 0.03)	(3.4, 0.9)	(1, 0.7)	(0.6, 0.4)

six eggs, both models are able to capture the dynamics of the rapid increase of the ICG intensity in the first few seconds. However, the basic model $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ fails to mimic complex dynamics, as they occur, e.g., for Egg 3. However, for Egg 1 (top left plot), there is no clear peak and drop in the measured signal and both models are able to accurately approximate $I_{dist}(x_{R3}, t)$. For the remaining eggs, $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ fails to capture the exact dynamics of $I_{dist}(x_{R_i}, t)$ for $t > 5$ s until the *steady state phase* is reached. For Egg 20 (bottom left plot), $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ approximates some of the characteristic peaks of $I_{dist,1}(x_{R4}, t)$ around 4.5 s, 8 s, and 11 s, but is not able to capture them completely. In summary, it can be observed from Fig. 12 that the extended parametric model in (8) provides a better approximation of the distribution dynamics of molecules in the CAM model during the *transient* and *steady state phases* than the basic model in (7). We further investigate the accuracy of both parametric models for the dataset in Section V-A4.

For the measurements considered in Fig. 12, the estimates obtained for the parameters of $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ and $\hat{I}_{dist,2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ are shown in Table I. For $n = 2$, we show the estimated parameters of the same type as pairs (e.g., $(D_{eff}^{2,1}, D_{eff}^{2,2})$). Inspecting both Fig. 12 and Table I, there are two main observations. First, most of the estimated parameters are consistent in terms of the range of the estimated parameters. Second, there is a clear relationship between the presence of outliers in the estimated parameters for the basic model, $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$, and its performance to capture the dynamics of the measurements in certain eggs, compared to the extended model, $\hat{I}_{dist,2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$. In Fig. 12, we observe that for Egg 4, Egg 19, and Egg 24, $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ fails to capture the dynamics of the measurements. Accordingly, in Table I, we observe that there are outliers in the corresponding estimated parameter sets for $\hat{I}_{dist,1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$. For example, for Egg 19, the estimated effective diffusion coefficient, $D_{eff}^{1,1}$, is $10^{-11} m^2 s^{-1}$, which

Fig. 13: RMSE values calculated according to (14) for the approximations of $I_{\text{dist}}(x_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ by the basic parametric model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ (green bars) in (7) and the extended parametric model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ (red bars) in (8), for the eggs considered in Fig. 12.

is much smaller compared to the other estimated D_{eff} values. Also, for Egg 4 and Egg 24, the same comparably small values of D_{eff} were obtained. Moreover, for Egg 4 and Egg 24, distance $d_{\text{rx}}^{1,1}$ is estimated as 6 μm and 7 μm , respectively, which is much smaller compared to the other estimated d_{rx} values.

Figure 13 shows the RMSE between the measurement data of the ICG distribution and their approximations based on the proposed parametric models for the eggs considered in Fig. 12. The horizontal axis in Fig. 13 shows the ROI and egg number. The green and red bars show the RMSE values according to (14) for the approximations of the measurements $I_{\text{dist}}(x_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ by the basic model, $\text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1})$, and the extended parametric model, $\text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2})$, respectively. From Fig. 13, we observe that the accuracy of the approximation observed in Fig. 12 is consistent with the RMSE values. For example, for Egg 1, Fig. 12 suggests that both parametric models provide a good approximation of the measurement data, resulting in very low RMSE values in Fig. 13. In contrast, for Egg 3 and Egg 4, the basic parametric model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ yields significantly higher RMSE values compared to the extended model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$. This difference arises from the mismatch between the approximation by the basic model and the measurement data, which is evident in Fig. 12. For Egg 20, the RMSE values of both approximations are comparable, which is also evident from Fig. 12, as both models capture the dynamics with good accuracy. In conclusion, the analysis of the RMSE values in Fig. 13 confirms that the extended model consistently outperforms the basic model for all eggs considered in Fig. 12.

4) *Estimated Parameters and RMSE of the Dataset:* In this section, we analyze the complete dataset of measurements of the particle distribution in the CAM model (see [27]) along with the parameters estimated via curve fitting of the parametric models described in Section IV-A2. In particular, we investigate the accuracy of the approximations obtained for the basic (7) and the extended (8) parametric models. Figure 14 shows the RMSE values (14) for the approximation of the measurements $I_{\text{dist}}(x_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ by the basic and extended models for all 69 ROIs in the dataset. On the horizontal

axis, the egg numbers and ROIs are shown, and the vertical axis provides the corresponding RMSE values. The green and red bars represent the RMSE values obtained for the basic parametric model, $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ in (7), and the extended parametric model, $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ in (8), respectively. The green and red horizontal lines are the thresholds to characterize the best 15% of the $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ and $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ approximations based on the RMSE values. These thresholds are denoted by $\tau_n(15\%)$, $n \in \{1, 2\}$. We note that, due to the high variability in the estimated parameters, we decided to not rely on the mean or median as representative values. Instead, we tightened the selection criteria and defined “good approximations” as those having the lowest 15% of RMSE values. The table in the top left corner of Fig. 14 summarizes the performance of $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ and $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ across all ROIs in the dataset, by the mean, minimum, and maximum RMSE values. Additionally, the table presents the threshold values $\tau_n(15\%)$ for both $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ and $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$.

From Fig. 14, we can observe that the $\text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2})$ values obtained for the extended model (red bars) are always smaller than the $\text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1})$ values for the basic model (green bars). This confirms the observation previously made in Fig. 13 that the approximation based on the extended model (8) outperforms that based on the basic model (7) for the complete dataset. However, it can be also observed that in some cases the basic model provides a similar accuracy as the extended model (e.g., Egg 1, Egg 2, Egg 11). The accuracy heavily depends on the egg, considered ROI, and foremost on the dynamics of the particle propagation. For example, the dynamics of the measurement in Egg 1 in ROI 3, top left plot of Fig. 12, are very smooth, and both models provide a very accurate fit, yielding similarly low RMSE values.

Figure 15 shows the parameters estimated via curve fitting for the basic and extended model, in six sub-figures. Each sub-figure visualizes pairwise correlations within the parameter set $\{d_{\text{inj}}, L_{\text{eff}}, D_{\text{eff}}, d_{\text{rx}}, \text{DED}, v_{\text{eff}}\}$. Here, L_{eff} , D_{eff} , d_{rx} , and v_{eff} are obtained via curve fitting, whereas DED and d_{inj} are measured. The gray circles indicate the estimated parameters corresponding to approximations with RMSE values above $\tau_n(15\%)$, i.e., $\{\mathcal{P}^n | \text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},n}) > \tau_n(15\%)\}$. The green markers show parameters estimated based on the basic model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ with RMSEs below $\tau_1(15\%)$, i.e., $\{\mathcal{P}^1 | \text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}) < \tau_1(15\%)\}$. For the extended model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$, there are pairs for each estimated parameter as two sets are considered for $n = 2$. Therefore, the red triangle and rectangle markers in Figure 15 denote the estimated parameters belonging to parameter sets $\mathcal{P}^{2,1}$ and $\mathcal{P}^{2,2}$ for the extended parametric model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$, i.e., $\{\mathcal{P}^{2,1} | \text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}) < \tau_2(15\%)\}$ and $\{\mathcal{P}^{2,2} | \text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}) < \tau_2(15\%)\}$.

Figure 15 (a) shows the estimated effective length L_{eff} on the horizontal axis and the measured injection distance, d_{inj} , on the vertical axis. It can be observed that the estimated L_{eff} values are in the same order of magnitude as the distance measured in the CAM model. This observation suggests that the actual range of the channel length is 2.5 – 5 cm. Figure 15 (b) shows the correlation between the estimated L_{eff}

Fig. 14: RMSE values for the complete dataset calculated according to (14) for the approximation of $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ by the basic parametric model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ (green bars) in (7), and the extended model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ (red bars) in (8), respectively. The horizontal green and red lines are the thresholds to indicate the best 15% of the approximations. The table in the top left shows the mean, minimum, maximum, and $\tau_n(15\%)$ of the RMSEs corresponding to the curve fitting of $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ and $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ to $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$.

and D_{eff} values. First, it can be observed that the estimated D_{eff} values with $\text{RMSE} < \tau_n(15\%)$ are consistently within the range $10^{-6} - 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The estimated effective diffusion coefficient, D_{eff} , is several orders of magnitude larger than the molecular diffusion coefficient [80]. This is in agreement with the observation that, in blood vessels, the combined effects of fluid flow, particularly the parabolic velocity profile in arteries, and molecular diffusion lead to a phenomenon known as Taylor dispersion [81]. Taylor dispersion leads to a significantly increased effective diffusion coefficient compared to molecular diffusion alone [82]. Moreover, we can observe that D_{eff} increases from $10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, when the estimated value of L_{eff} increases from 0.5 cm to 7 cm. This observation indicates that larger D_{eff} (more dispersion) values are often obtained jointly with larger L_{eff} values. This is directly correlated to the dynamics of the measurements shown in Fig. 12, i.e., when the measurements are more dispersive (smoother increase and fewer peaks), the models account for this behavior by larger D_{eff} and L_{eff} values. For example, the dynamics of the measured particle distribution in Egg 1 (top left in Fig. 12) are much smoother than those of Egg 20 (bottom left in Fig. 12), and therefore, the estimated D_{eff} and L_{eff} values are larger for Egg 1 compared to Egg 20. Figure 15 (c) shows the injection distance measured for the CAM model, d_{inj} , between the injection point and the ROI located at $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}$ over the estimated d_{rx} values. We observe that the estimated values of the observation point, d_{rx} , are in agreement with d_{inj} . This observation confirms that the estimates obtained for d_{rx} are in a reasonable range. Inspecting

the gray line (i.e., $d_{\text{rx}} = d_{\text{inj}}$) in Fig. 15 (c), it can be observed that most of the estimated d_{rx} values with $\text{RMSE} < \tau_n(15\%)$ are below this line, indicating that the estimated d_{rx} is larger than d_{inj} . This observation is reasonable because most of the vessels are curved and obviously the length of the vessel between the injection point and the ROI is larger than the straight line connecting both points. Figure 15 (d) shows the DED on the vertical axis and the estimated D_{eff} values on the horizontal axis. Inspecting only the estimated D_{eff} values with $\text{RMSE} < \tau_n(15\%)$, it can be observed that the variance of the estimated values decreases with increasing DED. One reason for this could be that eggs at higher DEDs, i.e., more developed and older eggs, have larger vessels that mainly dominate the particle distribution processes. Consequently, the transport dynamics and physical channel in those eggs more closely align with the assumptions of our analytical model, which is based on molecular advection-diffusion in a closed-loop system⁴. Figures 15 (e) and (f) show the relationship between the DED and the estimated L_{eff} and v_{eff} values, respectively. First, for both parameters, it can be observed that the variance of the estimated values also decreases as the DED increases. Moreover, from Fig. 15 (f) it can be observed that the estimated v_{eff} values are consistently in the range from $10^{-2} - 10 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$, which is also within the range expected from the literature for velocities inside the CAM vascular

⁴This observation suggests that more reliable estimates can be obtained in older eggs. Therefore, we will investigate the correlation between the estimated parameters and the DED further by extending our experimental studies to older eggs in future work.

system (see Section II-E).

Table II shows the mean values and the 70% confidence intervals (CIs) of the estimated parameters shown in Fig. 15. From Table II it can be observed that the mean values of all estimated parameters cluster around similar values and lie within the 70% CIs. For example, the mean of the estimated D_{eff} values is in the same order of magnitude for all considered parameter sets, including those with $\text{RMSE} > \tau(15\%)$. This observation reveals a consistent trend across different models. Furthermore, the parameters seem to be representative of the CAM model, making them suitable for future theoretical research particularly in characterizing closed-loop channels inspired by the CAM model. The analysis of the parametric models for the distribution of molecules in the CAM during the *transient* and *steady state phases* showed that both the basic model in (7) and the extended model in (8) are capable of approximating the distribution dynamics while providing reasonable estimates of the physical parameters.

B. Accumulation Phase

1) *Measurement Process*: As described in Section IV-A3 the *accumulation phase* starts after the *steady state phase*, i.e., $t > t_{\text{acc}}$. Hence, the measurement time was increased to approximately one hour. To overcome the challenge of possible bleeding after removing the injection needle, we fixed the syringe throughout the measurement time (see Fig. 2). We used 20 eggs, but so far only two were successfully measurable. The percentage of failure is higher in this case because the liver has to remain visible for the whole observation time⁵. However, due to the embryo's movement the liver position changes and may move under the egg shell or be blocked by other tissue. Since only two successful measurements could be obtained, they are not yet part of the published dataset. In the future, we will extend the dataset after obtaining a sufficient number of successful measurements for the molecule accumulation in the embryo's liver.

2) *Molecule Accumulation in the Liver*: Figure 16 shows the measured ICG fluorescence intensity $I(x_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ over time (curves with blue markers). The ROI \mathcal{R} on the right hand side of Fig. 16 indicates the region where the liver of the embryo is located. The green solid curves corresponds to the approximation of the fluorescence intensity during the *transient* and *steady state phases*, obtained by fitting the extended parametric model (8) to the measurement data. The red solid curves represent the approximation of the fluorescence intensity during the *accumulation phase*, obtained by fitting $\hat{I}_{\text{acc}}(\mathcal{C}, t)$ in (9) to the measurement data. Moreover, the transition time between the *steady state phase* and the *accumulation phase* $t = t_{\text{acc}}$ is shown by a vertical dashed line. The results shown in Fig. 16 confirm our modeling assumptions made in Section III-B, i.e., that the molecule distribution process inside the CAM model can be divided into three distinct phases. It can be observed that the *accumulation phase* starts after the *steady state phase*, where the fluorescence intensity in the region of

⁵The unsuccessful measurements (eggs) are not wasted as we used them for other experiments and data generation for the *transient* and *steady state phases*.

the liver slowly starts to increase. Moreover, we can observe from Fig. 16 that the proposed simple parametric model for the accumulation in (9) is in very good agreement with the measurement data, which is confirmed by the $\text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{acc}})$ values, i.e., $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (Egg 36) and $3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (Egg 37). For both experiments, the parameter sets \mathcal{C} estimated via the fitting process are in the same range, indicating the validity of the proposed accumulation model.

VI. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

In the previous sections, we have shown that the proposed parametric models are capable of approximating the molecule distribution and accumulation within the closed-loop CAM vascular system. However, there are still deviations from the measurement data, as the proposed models are not able to capture all environmental effects occurring in the CAM model.

In the following, we present two lists, where the first one is a discussion of modeling inaccuracies and approaches to further enhance the modeling accuracy in future work. The second list describes the experimental challenges and provides methods to further improve the experimental setup.

- The measurements of the fluorescence camera are 2D representations of a 3D system. Therefore, the measured fluorescence intensity at $x_{\mathcal{R}}$ can be interfered by the fluorescence of other vessels lying below the vessel of interest. Moreover, the measurements can be strongly influenced by random movements of the embryo.
- The model does not account for chemical reactions that may occur between the ICG molecules and other molecules in the environment. Moreover, the accumulation of ICG in the yolk bag and the embryo's organs and their binding to vessel walls need to be investigated. Specifically, the proposed model for the molecule accumulation in the liver should be extended to account for the actual binding and accumulation processes.
- The effective flow velocity v_{eff} in (4) is assumed to be constant. However, in the CAM model, the blood flow velocity is time varying rather than constant. Such fluctuations can increase molecular dispersion and lead to an asymmetric spatial concentration profile, in contrast to the symmetric profile observed for a constant flow velocity. This time dependent behavior should be taken into account in future modeling efforts.
- The enhanced performance achieved with the extended parametric model (8) may arise from several factors. Each term in the summation in (8) could correspond to a different dominant circulatory pathway with different effective length and flow characteristics. Alternatively, one component might represent the main circulatory path, while the other ones capture the aggregated effects of secondary branching and delayed pathways. Gaining more insight into the physical interpretation of the summation terms in (8) is an important direction for future work.

Next, we highlight future research directions for improving the experimental setup.

- One of the challenges in monitoring particle propagation inside the CAM model is the embryo's movement. In the

Fig. 15: Parameters estimated via fitting using the parametric models introduced in Section IV. Estimated parameters with RMSE above threshold $\tau_n(15\%)$ are shown by gray circles. Parameters estimated by fitting the basic model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}(\mathcal{P}^1, t)$ to the measurements with RMSEs below $\tau_1(15\%)$ are shown by green markers. Pairs of estimated parameters obtained via fitting the extended model $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ to the measurements with RMSEs below $\tau_2(15\%)$ are shown by red triangles and rectangles.

TABLE II: Mean values and 70% CIs of the estimated parameters shown in Fig. 15.

	$D_{\text{eff}} [\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}]$		$v_{\text{eff}} [\text{mm s}^{-1}]$		$L_{\text{eff}} [\text{cm}]$		$d_{\text{rx}} [\text{cm}]$	
	Mean	70% CI	Mean	70% CI	Mean	70% CI	Mean	70% CI
$\{\mathcal{P}^n \text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},n}) > \tau_n(15\%) \}$	$6.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$(3.7 \cdot 10^{-8}, 1 \cdot 10^{-5})$	3.8	(0.2, 8.5)	3.6	(1.2, 5.6)	1.7	(0.4, 3.4)
$\{\mathcal{P}^1 \text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},1}) < \tau_1(15\%) \}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$(1.4 \cdot 10^{-6}, 8.7 \cdot 10^{-6})$	3.5	(0.2, 9)	3.4	(1.5, 5.1)	1.7	(1, 2.6)
$\{\mathcal{P}^{2,1} \text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}) < \tau_2(15\%) \}$	$5.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$(3.1 \cdot 10^{-6}, 7.6 \cdot 10^{-6})$	3	(1.2, 5.8)	4	(2.3, 4.7)	2.2	(0.6, 3.9)
$\{\mathcal{P}^{2,2} \text{RMSE}(\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}) < \tau_2(15\%) \}$	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$(0.3 \cdot 10^{-6}, 8.2 \cdot 10^{-6})$	1.6	(0.03, 2.4)	3.5	(1.3, 5.9)	1.4	(0.7, 2.7)

future, we plan to minimize motion-induced artifacts. In particular, the embryo could be immobilized by placing the egg in ice chips for 20 min to 90 min or by dropping 5 mg Ketamine onto the CAM model surface [83].

- Monitoring the CAM continuously for long intervals (e.g., days) is crucial for studying long term effects. However, we cannot keep the eggs outside the incubator for extended periods of time since the environment must maintain certain levels of temperature and humidity. Another reason is the immunodeficiency of the CAM,

which makes it vulnerable to contamination. Hence, in the future, we plan to install our measurement setup inside an incubator.

- Repeatability of the experiments is crucial for more consistent and more interpretable results. Currently, the injection procedure is performed individually and by hand for every measurement. Therefore, to obtain repeatable measurements with high confidence, we plan to develop a setup with micro-injectors in the future.
- In this paper, we considered only one injection of a

Fig. 16: Experimental and fitting results of ICG distribution in the embryo's liver. The *transient* and *steady state* phases are approximated by $\hat{I}_{\text{dist},2}(\mathcal{P}^2, t)$ based on (8). The *accumulation phase* is approximated by $\hat{I}_{\text{acc}}(\mathcal{C}, t)$ based on (9). The blue markers correspond to the measured signal. The vertical dashed line indicates t_{acc} . The photos on the right hand side show the injection point and the ROIs.

fixed amount of ICG (50 μL) to obtain the “impulse response” of the system. In the future, we will extend our experiments to different amounts of ICG to study the dependency on the injected ICG concentration and to repeated injections within one measurement.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced the CAM model as a versatile *in vivo* MC testbed as an important step to enable the transition from proof-of-concept MC systems towards practical applications. The CAM model consists of a closed-loop cardiovascular system including blood circulation and organs, and therefore provides a realistic environment for the validation and optimization of MC technology. We introduced an analytical model for the diffusion and flow of molecules in dispersive closed-loop systems and validated it by PBS. We experimentally investigated and measured the distribution of the fluorescent molecule ICG in the CAM model, and created and published a dataset of 69 measurements in 25 different eggs. From the measurements, we identified three different phases for the molecule distribution in the CAM model, i.e., the *transient phase*, *steady state phase*, and *accumulation phase*. The *transient phase* corresponds to the quick distribution of the molecules in the CAM's vascular system. The *steady state phase* starts after the *transient phase*, where the ICG concentration remains approximately constant. In the *accumulation phase*, molecules start to leave the vascular system and accumulate in the liver of the chick embryo. Based on the derived analytical model, we proposed two parametric models to approximate the distribution of ICG molecules in the CAM model during the *transient* and *steady state* phases. Our results showed that the proposed parametric models are capable of accurately approximating the molecule distribution inside the CAM model. Moreover, we investigated the overall approximation performance of the proposed models in terms of the RMSE. Our results revealed that the estimated parameters

that were obtained by fitting the parametric models to the measurements are consistent and partly in a plausible range compared to empirically observed parameters. Furthermore, we proposed a simple parametric model to approximate the accumulation of molecules in the liver of the embryo during the *accumulation phase*. Based on a small experimental study, we demonstrated that the proposed model successfully captures the effects occurring in the *accumulation phase*. Finally, we discussed challenges and outlined future research directions, where the focus was particularly placed on the extension of the developed analytical models to account for more relevant environmental effects inside the CAM model, e.g., chemical reactions, and on the improvement of the testbed setup.

APPENDIX A METHODS

For all experiments, chicken eggs were incubated at a constant temperature of 37.8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, a pCO_2 of 5 %, and humidity calibrated to 63 %. The eggs were rotated during the first four days of incubation to prevent the embryos from adhering to the shell membranes and to minimize the risk of vascular damage when opening the eggshells. The shells were opened on DED 4, before the CAM fully fused to the shell membranes, to avoid damaging the developing vasculature [47]. To this end, the air entrapment in the egg was localized with a light source and a hole of approximately 2 mm \times 2 mm was cut with sterile tweeters into the overlaying eggshell to introduce atmospheric negative pressure. A second hole of approximately 5 mm \times 5 mm was introduced at the longitudinal side of the egg. The holes were covered with Leukosilk® (BSN medical, Hamburg, Germany) and the eggs were returned to the incubator in a static position. ICG was administered intravenously to assess intratumoral perfusion. The ICG solution was prepared by diluting it to a concentration of 50 μM in 0.9 % sodium chloride, resulting in a final dosage of 0.3 mg kg^{-1} , additionally 5 % blood was added to the solution. Fluorescence peaked at a wavelength of 830 nm. Imaging was conducted using the Medtronic EleVision IR (VSIII) fluorescence system (Medtronic®, Meerbusch, Germany), which operates in the near-infrared spectrum. The injection process employed a 1 mL syringe (Norm-Ject HENKE, Tuttlingen, Germany) fitted with a 33 G needle (Hypodermic Needles, 33 G 0.20 mm \times 4 mm, MESORAM, Putzbrunn, Germany). The video recordings of the ICG molecule distribution were performed with an ICG camera (EleVision™ IR Platform, Medtronic). The video data analysis (Fluorescence tracking in ROIs) was done with the Matlab Fluorescence Tracker App⁶. We measured the fluorescent intensity of pure ICG beside the egg and used it as a reference signal. This reference signal was then subtracted from the fluorescent intensity measured in the desired ROI. This subtraction was essential to account for variations in ICG fluorescence caused by the inherent properties of the ICG molecule and automatic light intensity rescaling performed by the camera. The sampling time step

⁶<https://matlab.mathworks.com/open/github/v1?repo=mathworks/Fluorescence-Tracker-App>

Δt was 10^{-4} s and 10^{-2} s for $I_{\text{dist}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$ and $I_{\text{acc}}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{R}}, t)$, respectively.

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